

Hannah's protocol

To: rory.rory@hotmail.com
Cc:
Subject: Protocol
From: hannah-p@gmail.com

Dear Rory,

Thank you for delegating your voting rights in the board meeting to me. After wading through the boring agenda items, things got exciting when it came to establishing a research integrity policy. I initially didn't know what to do or what the term research integrity meant, but the arguments in the room finally convinced me to vote in favour. I hope I represented you well with my vote. Would you have voted for a research integrity policy, too? Here is a rough transcript of the meeting. See you tomorrow?

All the best,
Hannah

Protocol

Agenda topic 5: Research integrity policy

Discussion:
Do we need a research integrity policy?

Member 1:

This is really, vitally important; we need to have solid, transparent rules around ethics and research methods, or this institution's reputation will be a joke.

(General agitation; Whispers in the hall; Call from other member: "Don't overdo it!")

Member 2:

You can't regulate honesty. There are just too many different circumstances to be able to account for all of them with individual rules, and we certainly don't need more administration here. You can only encourage people to do the right thing or hire people who have values like honesty and integrity, and the institution already has a code of conduct for that.

(Call from other member: "Exactly, why more paperwork?")

Member 3:

Doesn't each discipline have its own professional code and standards anyway? A research integrity policy for the whole institution doesn't make any sense, as accepted practices differ too greatly from field to field.

(Sounds of approval and positive comments)

Member 1:

A research integrity statement is needed to establish values and processes. These would help address specific issues like authorship, scientific rigour and data management, as well as aid in investigations of scientific misconduct.

(General agitation; Call from other member: "Why would we need that?")

Member 4:

It's all about being clear on what we expect at this university and giving people the tools to navigate tricky issues. We believe you can't have research excellence without integrity in research.

Meeting organis...
Research integrity

Thank you to everyo
attended. Attached
minutes from the m

Rory

Board meeting

Hi Hannah, could yo
board meeting? I wo
delegate my vote.

